

Mercury Content in Edible Part of *Otolithes Ruber* Marketed in Hamedan, Iran

L. Tayebi , S. Sobhanardakani , A. Farmany and M. Cheraghi

Abstract—In this research the level of mercury is analyzed in muscle tissue of *Otolithes ruber* reetailed in Hamedan, Iran were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrometry after wet digestion. Analysis of mercury was carried out by spectrophotometrically. The average concentration of Hg in muscle tissue of *Otolithes ruber* was 0.030 ± 0.026 $\mu\text{g/g}$ so lower than to compare with the Maximum Allowable Concentration determined by FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission.

Keywords—mercury, *Otolithes ruber*, edible part, Hamedan

I. INTRODUCTION

MANUFACTURE, traffic, utilization and disposal of many modern products cause trace metal release into the aquatic environment and increasing attention is paid on how humans be affected by this. Biomonitoring of trace elements is essential to assess ecosystem health [5], [12], [15], [24], [25]. Heavy metals can be categorized as: potentially toxic (aluminium, arsenic, cadmium, antimony lead, mercury) probably essential like nickel, vanadium, cobalt and essential like copper, zinc, selenium etc. [22], [26], [32], [37], [38]. The essential metals can also be toxic when excessively elevated intake is of concern. There has been a growing interest to find out the heavy metal contamination level of public food supplies, particularly fish and fishery products. Marine organisms, especially fish, accumulate contaminants from the aquatic environment and therefore fish are used as good indicators of heavy metals in aquatic systems [20], [29]. Therefore fish is the main source of trace elements like mercury in human diet. Approximately 90% of human health risk related to fish consumption is associated to mercury-contaminated fish [9], [11], [30]. In the other hand, fishes are widely consumed because it has high protein content, low saturated fat and also contains omega fatty acids known to support good health. Fishes are constantly exposed to heavy metals because of pollution from chemicals and contamination in waters. Fish muscle is commonly analysed to determine contaminant concentrations and to assess the health risks because it is the main part consumed by humans. The levels of contaminants especially heavy metals in fish are of particular interest because of the potential risk to humans who consume them [8]. The accumulation of heavy metals of fish was size specific, with higher concentrations of metals generally found in smaller fish. Contamination of heavy metals also varied as a function of the different localities.

1- Department of Environment, Malayer University, Malayer, Iran (phone: 00988114494000; fax: 00988114494143; e-mail: l_tayebi@iauh.ac.ir).

2- Department of Environment, Hamedan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Hamedan, Iran (e-mail: s_sobhan@iauh.ac.ir, cheraghi_md@iauh.ac.ir)

3- Young Researchers Club, Hamedan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Hamedan, Iran (e-mail: a.farmany@usa.com).

The heavy metal levels of fish and other fishery products are widely documented in the literature [1], [2], [4], [6], [7], [13], [17], [29], [33], [34], [36], [38].

Hamedan is generally transported by the heavy vehicles from Persian Gulf. No data exist on trace metal levels of fish species reetailed in Hamedan, Iran. According to neurotoxic effect of mercury, it is listed as one of the six, most dangerous chemical substances by International Program of Chemical Safety (IPSC) [10], [28]. So the present study was carried out to determine the levels of Hg in muscle tissue of one of important commercially available fish species (*Otolithes ruber*) in Hamedan, Iran.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Chemical and reagents

All chemical reagents were of analytical grade, purchased from Merck (Germany). All solutions were prepared with de-ionized water. Stock standard solution of Hg(II) (1000 mg/L) were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of metal salts/oxid dissolving in doubly distilled water and diluting to 1000 ml in volumetric flask.

B. Apparatus

Mercury absorbance measurements were carried out on a Scinco's PDA UV-Vis. Spectrophotometer (photodiode array) equipped with 1.0-cm quartz cells. Voltammetric measurements were carried out using a polarographic processor; model 746 VA (Metrohm), in combination with a polarographic stand model, 747 VA (Metrohm). The electrode stand consist of a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as working electrode, a double junction Ag/AgCl (3M KCl, saturated AgCl, and 3M KCl in the bridge) as reference electrode and platinum wire, with considerably larger surface area than that of HMDE, as auxiliary electrode. Potentials quoted are relative to Ag/AgCl reference electrode. Stirring was carried out by a large Teflon rod with 2000 rpm speed. A 780 pH Meter (Metrohm), equipped with a combined Ag/AgCl glass electrode was used for pH measurements. Eppendorf reference variable micropipettes were used to pipette microlitre volume of solutions. All glassware was soaked overnight in 10% (v/v) nitric acid, followed by washing with 10% (v/v) hydrochloric acid, and rinsed with double distilled water and dried before using.

C. Sample preparation

Although voltammetric techniques are inherently precise and accurate, the results obtained using these techniques may be invalidated due to contamination caused by poor sample handling and preparation. Therefore, stringent conditions should be routinely used for analysis, particularly when dealing with trace concentrations. For example, all reagents, standard solutions, etc., should be ultra-pure, and all glassware

needs to be scrupulously cleaned. Similarly, stringent conditions should also be used for sampling and the pretreatment of samples; these two stages should be simplified as much as possible to minimize the potential for sample loss and contamination. Different complex matrices of the analytical sample require prior mineralization for most analytical methods, and this step is critical in the whole analytical procedure for the determination of metal concentration. Sample digestion techniques, such as microwave, and conventional acid digestion method for heavy metal determination have been used widely for the dissolution of target elemental analyses. These digestions techniques, however, require the use of concentrated mineral acids and high temperatures. Fish samples were cleaned with sterile distilled water and then dissected. Two grams of muscle tissue of the fish was removed and weighed for the analysis of Mercury. For estimation of Mercury content 2 g of muscle tissue was taken in a 100-ml Borosil beaker. To this, 2 ml of HNO₃ and 1 ml of HClO₄ was added and kept for digestion on a hot plate at 100°C till complete digestion was achieved (Complete digestion involves removal of organic matter by reacting with acids.). It was ensured that the residue obtained after digestion was free from organic matter which acts as impurities in Mercury analysis [14], [23], [27]. Residue was reconstituted using 1 M of 10 ml Hydrochloric acid (HCl) for further analysis.

D. Sample analysis

To quantify the concentration of Hg(II) in muscle tissues of *Otolithes ruber* species by anodic stripping voltammetry, in the electrochemical cell 5 mL of each sample solution and 1 mL acetate-acetic acid buffer solution were transferred and diluted to 10 mL by doubly distilled water. The solution was deaerated by passing pure nitrogen for 5 min. The deposition potential was applied to a fresh mercury drop while the solution was stirred. After the deposition step and further 10 sec. (equilibrium time) the voltammograms were recorded. Different concentrations of the standard metal ion were added to the cell, while keeping the deposition time constant. The solution was stirred and purged with nitrogen for 1 min. after each spike. The concentration of Hg(II) in the muscle tissues of *Otolithes ruber* are analyzed by spectrophotometric method [21].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of Hg was done by spectrophotometric method. Toxic metals contamination in edible parts of fish species is particular interest because of the potential risk to human health who consumes fish and fishery products. The result of this study shows that the average concentration of Mercury in muscle tissue of *Otolithes ruber* was 0.030±0.026 µg/g. This result is similar to other reports such as Rezayi *et al.*, 2011; Emami Khansari *et al.*, 2005; Voegborlo *et al.*, 1999. Therefore the average concentration of Mercury was lower than to compare with the Maximum Allowable Concentration determined by FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission [18], [19]. So seem consumption the edible parts of *Otolithes ruber* that marketed in hamedan to be safe for consumers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to The Islamic Azad University-Hamedan Branch for providing facilities to conduct and complete this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] I.M. Adekunle, and M.F. Akinyemi, "Lead levels of certain consumer products in Nigeria: A case study of smoked fish foods from Abeokuta," Food and Chemical Toxicology, 2004, 42: 1463-1468.
- [2] H. Agah, M. Leermakers, M. Elskens, S.M.R. Fatemi, and W. Baeyens, "Accumulation of trace metals in the muscles and liver tissues of five fish species from the Persian gulf," Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 2009, 157: 499-514.
- [3] T. Agusa, T. Kunito, G. Yasunaga, H. Iwata, A. Subramanian, A. Ismail, and S. Tanabe, "Concentrations of trace elements in marine fish and its risk assessment in Malaysia," Marine Pollution Bulletin, 2005, 51(8-12): 896-911.
- [4] V. Alibabić, N. Vahčić, and M. Bajramović, "Bioaccumulation of Metals in Fish of Salmonidae Family and the Impact on Fish Meat Quality," Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 2007, 131: 349-364.
- [5] O.A. Al-Khashman, "Determination of metal accumulation in deposited street dusts in Amman, Jordan," Environmental Geochemistry and Health, 2007, 29: 1-10.
- [6] I. Al-Saleh, and I. Al-Doush, "Mercury Content in Shrimp and Fish Species the Gulf Coast of Saudi Arabia," Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology, 2001, 68: 576-583.
- [7] T.M. Ansari, S. Mahboob, T. Hanif, M. Arif, and A. Salam, "Dry ashing or wet digestion? A comparative study for estimation of zinc and calcium in freshwater fish samples by atomic absorption spectrometry," Journal of the Chemical Society of Pakistan, 2005, 27: 90-94.
- [8] W. Ashraf, "Accumulation of heavy metals in kidney and heart tissues of Epinephelus Microdon fish from the Arabian Gulf," Environmental Monitoring And Assessment, 2005, 101: 311-316.
- [9] M.J. Berry, and N.V.C. Ralston, "Mercury toxicity and the mitigating role of selenium," EcoHealth, 2008, 5 (4): 456-459
- [10] S. Bhattacharyya, P. Chaudhuri, S. Dutta, and S. Chandra Santra, "Assessment of total mercury level in fish collected from East Calcutta Wetlands and Titagarh sewage fed aquaculture in West Bengal, India," Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology, 2010, 84: 618-622.
- [11] J. Burger and M. Gochfeld, "Heavy metals in commercial fish in New Jersey," Environmental Research, 2005, 99: 403-41.
- [12] U. Cevik, N. Damla, B. Koz, and S. Kaya, "Radiological characterization around the afsin-elbistan coal-fired power plant in Turkey. Energy & Fuels, 22(1), 428-432.
- [13] O. Dalman, A. Demirak, and A. Balci, "Determination of heavy metals (Cd, Pb) and trace elements (Cu, Zn) in sediments and fish of Southeastern Aegean Sea (Turkey) by atomic absorption spectrometry," Food Chemistry, 2006, 95: 157-162.
- [14] A. Deshpande, S. Bhendigeri, T. Shirsekar, D. Dhaware, and R. N. Khandekar, "Analysis of heavy metals in marine fish from Mumbai Docks," Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 2009, 159: 493-500.
- [15] M. Duran, Y. Kara, G.K. Akyildiz, and A. Ozdemir, "Antimony and heavy metals accumulation in some macroinvertebrates in the Yesilirmak River (N Turkey) near the Sb-mining area," Bulletin of Environment Contamination and Toxicology, 2007, 78: 395-399.
- [16] F. Emami Khansari, M. Ghazi-Khansari, and M. Abdollahi, "Heavy metals content of canned tuna fish," Food Chemistry, 2005, 93: 293-296.
- [17] G. Falco, J.M. Llobet, A. Bocio, and J.L. Domingo, "Daily intake of arsenic, cadmium, mercury and lead by consumption of edible marine species," Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 2006, 54: 61-62.
- [18] Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations and World Health Organization (FAO/WHO), "Evaluation of certain food additives and the contaminations mercury, lead and cadmium," WHO Technical Report, Series No. 505, 1989.
- [19] Food and Agriculture/World Health Organization (FAO/WHO), "Evaluation of Certain Food Additives and the Contaminants Mercury, Cadmium and Lead", WHO Technical Report Series No. 505, Geneva, 1972.
- [20] F. Henry, R. Amara, L. Courcot, D. Lacouture, and M.L. Bertho, "Heavy metals in four fish species from the French coast of the Eastern

- English Channel and Southern Bight of North Sea," *Environment International*, 2004, 30: 675-683.
- [21] M. Humaira Khan, A. Jamaluddin and M. Iqbal Bhangar, "A Simple Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Level Mercury Using 1,5-Diphenylthiocarbazon Solubilized in Micelle," *Analytical Sciences*, 2005, 21: 507.
- [22] N. Jayaraju, B.C.S.R. Reddy, and K.R. Reddy, "The response of benthic foraminifera to various pollution sources: A study from Nellore Coast, East Coast of India," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 2008, 142 (1-3): 319-323.
- [23] R.N. Khandekar, U.C. Mishra, and K.G. Vohra, "Environmental lead exposure of anurban Indian population," *The Science of the Total Environment*, 1984, 40: 269-278.
- [24] C. Mico, M. Peris, J. Sanchez, and L. Recatala, "Heavy metal content of agricultural soils in a Mediterranean semiarid area: The Segura River Valley (Alicante, Spain)," *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, 2006, 4: 363-372.
- [25] I. Narin, M. Soylak, and M. Dogan, "Traffic pollution in Nigde-Turkiye: Investigation of trace element contents of soil samples," *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*, 1997, 6: 749-752.
- [26] Y. Ni, C. Huang, and S. Kokot, "Simultaneous determination of iron and aluminium by differential kinetic spectrophotometric method and chemometrics," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 2007, 259(2): 209-218.
- [27] R. Raghunath, R.M. Tripathi, R.N. Khandekar, and K.S.V. Nambi, "Retention times of Pb, Cd, Cu and Zn in children's blood," *The Science of the Total Environment*, 1997, 207: 133-139.
- [28] L.J. Raymond, and N.V.C. Ralston, "Mercury: Selenium interactions and health implications," *Seychelles Medical and Dental Journal*, 2004, 7(1): 72-77.
- [29] M. Rezayi, A.S. Esmaeli, and T. Valinasab, "Mercury and Selenium Content in *Otolithes ruber* and *Psettodes erumei* from Khuzestan Shore, Iran," *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 2011, 86: 511-514.
- [30] J. Ruelas-Inzunza, G. Meza-Lopez, and F. Paez-Osuna, "Mercury in fish that are of dietary importance from the coasts of Sinaloa (SE Gulf of California)," *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 2008, 21(3): 211-218.
- [31] A. Shokrollahi, M. Ghaedi, M.S. Niband, and H.R. Rajabi, "Selective and sensitive spectrophotometric method for determination of sub-micro-molar amounts of aluminium ion," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2007, 151(2-3): 642-648.
- [32] K. Szentmihalyi, and M. Then, "Examination of microelements in medicinal plants of the carpathian basin," *Acta Alimentaria*, 2007, 36: 231-236.
- [33] A. Turkmen, M. Turkmen, Y. Tepe, and I. Akyurt, "Heavy metals in three commercially valuable fish species from İskenderun Bay, Northern East Mediterranean Sea, Turkey," *Food Chemistry*, 2005, 91: 167-172.
- [34] M. Tuzen, and M. Soylak, "Determination of trace metals in canned fish marketed in Turkey," *Food Chemistry*, 2007, 101 (4): 1378-1382.
- [35] R.B. Voegborlo, A.M. El-Methnani, and M.Z. Abedin, "Mercury, cadmium and lead content of canned tuna fish," *Food Chemistry*, 1999, 67: 341-345.
- [36] J.G. Wiener, and D.J. Spry, "Toxicological significance of mercury in freshwater fish," p.297-339 in: Beyer WN, Heinz GH, Rdmon-Norwood AW (eds.). *Environmental Contamination in wildlife: Interpreting Tissue Concentration*. SETAC Special Publications Series. CRC Press, Inc. Lewis Publisher. Boca Raton, FL. 1996.
- [37] M.G. Yalcin, O. Aydin, and H. Elhatip, "Heavy metal contents and the water quality of Karasu Creek in Nigde, Turkey," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 2008, 137 (1-3): 169-178.
- [38] Y. Yildirim, Z. Gonulalan, I. Narinand M. Soylak, "Evaluation of trace heavy metal levels of some fish species sold at retail in Kayseri, Turkey," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 2009, 149: 223-228.